

ISic3611

I.Sicily inscription 3611

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Scicli

Provenance

fondo Picciona della contrada Scalonazzo, frazione di Sampierie

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6196

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645684

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2008.0599

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 58.1053

Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 215-216 no.94 fig.49

Rizzone, V.G. 2008. Iscrizioni tardoantiche del territorio di Scicli. In Militello, P. (eds.), *Scicli: archeologia e territorio*. Palermo. pp. 283-290. At 284-285 no.2 fig.25.2

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3611. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388825>